

Research Article

Vegetable Consumption Among Children: An Analysis of Preferences and Types of Vegetables

Kek Tain Chao^{1,*}, and Muhammad Syawal Amran²¹ Fakulti Pendidikan, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia; p130217@siswa.ukm.edu.my² Fakulti Pendidikan, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia; syawal@ukm.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6308-8757

* Correspondence: p130217@siswa.ukm.edu.my; +60125153621.

Abstract: *Vegetable are essential for the growth and development of children. Unfortunately, the average daily vegetable intake among children still falls below the recommended level. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to identify the categories of vegetable consumption among children and examine differences in vegetable intake based on gender and socioeconomic status. This study employed random sampling involving two Year 1 classes at an SJKC school in Melaka. A total of 50 students were selected as samples, consisting of 25 boys and 25 girls. The study utilized a quantitative survey design and was conducted in two phases. However, the researcher focused only on the first phase, which involved conducting a pilot study to analyse vegetable consumption data for the development of a module. The second phase will involve the development of a module using the Storytelling approach to influence children's behaviour toward vegetable consumption. The findings from descriptive analysis indicated that the majority of Year 1 students enjoy eating vegetables. The most preferred vegetable was broccoli, while the least preferred was eggplant. Meanwhile, inferential analysis revealed no significant relationship between gender and vegetable preference levels. However, a significant relationship was found between preference levels and household income. The implications of this study provide an important foundation for developing a module to enhance vegetable consumption among children in the second phase and offer preliminary insights for teachers regarding their students' dietary habits.*

Keywords: vegetable consumption; children.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Nutrition is an essential part of life, health, and human development. An unbalanced diet refers to a condition where food intake does not meet the necessary nutrient requirements for optimal health and bodily functions (Zubiaga, M. R. O., 2024). This includes deficiencies or excesses in the intake of nutrients such as carbohydrates, proteins, fats, vitamins, and minerals. An unbalanced diet can lead to various health problems, including malnutrition, obesity, diabetes, heart disease, and a weakened immune system (Zubiaga, M. R. O., 2024). Poor nutrition negatively impacts children's physical and mental development (De et al., 2019; Kirolos et al., 2022). Malnourished children tend to have weaker immune systems, making them more vulnerable to illnesses; it can also affect their ability to learn and develop intellectually (Bourke et al., 2016). Research findings indicate that malnutrition among children can result in several negative consequences, such as low school enrolment, depression, anxiety, poor academic achievement, and more (Amoadu et al., 2024; Fynn-Sackey & Abdul Salam, 2015).

It has been reported that children who maintain a healthy diet that includes vegetables have better mental health and overall well-being (Nekitsing et al., 2018). Sufficient vegetable intake can reduce the risk of chronic diseases such as cancer, diabetes, and heart disease (Hendrie et al., 2024). Vegetables also contribute to better mental well-being throughout life, making them an essential component of a balanced diet and a healthy lifestyle (Folkvord, F., Naderer, B., Coates, A., & Boyland, E., 2021). However, a family's socioeconomic status is one of the challenges in providing a balanced diet for children. Low-income families often lack access to a diet rich in healthy foods, including vegetables. Gender also influences a child's diet. Boys tend to consume more calories and high-fat foods, whereas girls may be more inclined to choose healthier and more nutritious foods (Birch et al., 1998).

Additionally, advancements in food technology have increased the availability of energy-dense and nutrient-poor food products, while globalization and urbanization have led to overall lifestyle changes—from home environments to children's self-regulation of their diet and the physical presence of parents to feed their children (Haines, J., 2019). In Brazil, data from the Food and Nutrition Surveillance System (SISVAN) in 2022 showed that 93% of children aged 5 to 9 had consumed ultra-processed foods the day before their consultation, whereas the prevalence of consuming natural or staple foods, such as beans, fruits, and vegetables, was low (Aguiar, I. W. O., et al., 2023). In Australia, only 6% of children met the recommended daily vegetable intake outlined in the Australian Dietary Guidelines (Mihreshahi et al., 2019). This situation is also observed in Malaysia, where the average daily vegetable intake among children under the age of 7 is only 1.07 servings of fruits and vegetables, far below the recommended five servings per day (Chong, K. H., et al., 2017). The SEANUTS study involving children in Southeast Asia also found that urban children in Malaysia consume only 1.62 servings of vegetables daily (Koo et al., 2016).

According to the Malaysian Dietary Guidelines for Children and Adolescents, children are recommended to consume at least three servings of vegetables per day to ensure a balanced diet and support healthy growth (Nutrition Division, Ministry of Health Malaysia, 2020). These guidelines pose a challenge for parents and teachers in encouraging children to develop a preference for vegetables. Therefore, the objective of this study is to identify categories of vegetable intake among children and the differences in consumption based on gender and socioeconomic status. This study is a pilot study, and the pilot study data will serve as supporting data for developing a storytelling module to be used in the second phase of the study to increase vegetable intake among children.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study employs a quantitative approach, utilizing a survey research design. This survey method is suitable for identifying the characteristics of a population using questionnaires, making the study's scope broader (Takona, J. P., 2024). The study is conducted in two phases. In the first phase, the researcher conducts a pilot study to analyse vegetable consumption data needed to develop a storytelling module. In the second phase, the researcher develops the module and applies the storytelling approach to influence children's behaviour towards vegetable consumption. This study focuses only on the first phase to obtain supporting data for the development of the storytelling module.

Beside that, study employs a random sampling method involving two Year 1 classes at an SJKC school in Melaka. The total number of pupils in both classes is 77. However, the researcher selects 50 samples, consisting of 25 boys and 25 girls. The selection is based on the pupils' interest in participating in the study and parental consent. The equal number of male and female pupils allows for gender comparisons in vegetable consumption preferences.

The research instrument used is a questionnaire adapted from the study by Katembu, S., Zahedi, A., Sind, S. M., Sommer, U., Kimamo, C., & Sommer, W. (2024). The questionnaire includes 10 images of vegetables for category selection. Each vegetable is assigned three response categories: “like”, “unsure”, and “dislike”. The questionnaire uses a traffic light scale: green for “like,” yellow for “unsure,” and red for “dislike” (Allen, I. E., & Seaman, C. A., 2007). Demographic data also include the number of pupils by gender and socioeconomic status.

The collected data is analysed using computer software. The results are processed with the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27.0. Descriptive analysis is conducted using frequency tests and cross-tabulation to identify vegetable consumption preferences among Year 1 pupils. Meanwhile, inferential analysis using the chi-square test is performed to examine the relationship between vegetable consumption preferences, gender, and household income.

3. FINDINGS

This study was conducted with a sample of 50 pupils, where demographic data such as gender and household income were analysed in the following table.

Table 1. Demographics of the Study Sample

Demographics		N	Percentage %
Gender	Male	25	50
	Female	25	50
Household Income	B40	29	58
	Non-B40	21	42

Table 1 shows that the study involved 50 samples, consisting of 25 male and 25 female pupils. In terms of household income, 29 pupils (58%) were from B40 households, while 21 pupils (42%) were from non-B40 households.

3.1 Identifying Vegetable Consumption Categories Among Children

The researcher provided pupils with a questionnaire to select their vegetable consumption category. Based on the questionnaire responses, the vegetable preference categories are summarized in the following table.

Table 2. Vegetable Preference Categories

Category	N	Percentage %
Like	220	44
Unsure	76	15.2
Dislike	204	40.8
Total	500	100

Table 2 analyses children's preferences for vegetables. A total of 44% (220 responses) indicated that pupils liked eating vegetables, showing that nearly half of the pupils enjoyed them. Meanwhile, 40.8% (204 responses) disliked vegetables, a number almost equal to those who liked them. Additionally, 15.2% (76 responses) were unsure about their vegetable preference. This data indicates that more pupils liked vegetables than disliked them, although the two groups were nearly balanced. The detailed breakdown of preferences for each type of vegetable is provided in the following table.

Table 3. Types of Vegetables and Preference Categories

Vegetable	Category	N	Percentage %
Broccoli	Like	33	66
	Unsure	9	18
	Dislike	8	16
Cucumber	Like	27	54
	Unsure	10	20
	Dislike	13	26
Cauliflower	Like	20	40
	Unsure	11	22
	Dislike	19	38
Carrot	Like	32	64
	Unsure	6	12
	Dislike	12	24
Water Spinach	Like	25	50
	Unsure	4	8
	Dislike	21	42
Okra	Like	19	38
	Unsure	5	10
	Dislike	26	52
Eggplant	Like	4	8
	Unsure	4	8
	Dislike	42	84
Long Beans	Like	12	24
	Unsure	12	24
	Dislike	26	52
Cabbage	Like	25	50
	Unsure	6	12
	Dislike	19	38
Sweet Potato	Like	23	46
	Unsure	9	18
	Dislike	18	36

Based on Table 3, an analysis of pupils' preferences for different vegetables reveals several trends. Overall, certain vegetables received positive responses, such as broccoli, cucumber, and carrots. Broccoli was liked by 66% (33 pupils), making it a popular vegetable. Similarly, 64% (32 pupils) liked carrots, and 54% (27 pupils) liked cucumbers, indicating that these three vegetables were well received among the pupils. Some veggies, however, were less popular. Eggplant received the highest dislike rate, with 84% (42 pupils) disliking it. Long beans and okra were the next most despised foods, with 52% (26 pupils) each.

Other vegetables such as cauliflower, water spinach, cabbage, and sweet potato showed a more balanced level of acceptance. For example, 50% of pupils liked water spinach and cabbage, while the remaining pupils were either unsure or disliked them. This suggests that these vegetables fall in the middle range between popularity and dislike, with pupils having mixed opinions. Overall, this analysis reflects pupils' views on different vegetable categories. Broccoli and carrots were among the most favoured vegetables, whereas eggplant and long beans were the least preferred.

3.2 Identifying Difference in Vegetable Consumption Based on Gender and Socioeconomic Status

This study aims to determine whether there are specific trends in vegetable selection and acceptance based on gender.

Table 4. Vegetable Preference Categories by Gender

Category	Male	Percentage %	Female	Percentage %
Like	9	36	10	40
Unsure	5	20	7	28
Dislike	11	44	8	32
Total	25	100	25	100

Based on Table 4, male and female pupils showed similar patterns in vegetable preferences. Among male pupils, 36% (9 pupils) liked vegetables, while 40% (10 pupils) of female pupils liked them, showing a slight 4% difference favouring females. For the "Unsure" category, 20% (5 male pupils) and 28% (7 female pupils) were uncertain about their vegetable preference, with a difference of 8% higher among females. In the "Dislike" category, 44% (11 male pupils) disliked vegetables, compared to 32% (8 female pupils), showing a 12% higher dislike rate among males. Thus, the analysis indicates that gender does not significantly impact vegetable preference, as the differences between male and female pupils are minimal.

Table 5. Vegetable Preference Categories by Socioeconomic Status

Category	B40	Percentage %	Non- B40	Percentage %
Like	3	10.3	16	76.2
Unsure	9	31.1	3	14.3
Dislike	17	58.6	2	9.5
Total	29	100	21	100

Based on Table 5, there is a significant difference in the category of liking vegetables between the B40 and Non-B40 groups. Among the B40 group, only 3 pupils or 10.3% indicated that they like vegetables. On the other hand, in the Non-B40 group, 16 pupils or 76.2% showed their liking for vegetables. This shows that pupils in the Non-B40 group have a higher tendency to like vegetables than pupils from the B40 group. For the "Unsure" category, 9 pupils from the B40 group or 31.1% showed their uncertainty about vegetables, while in the Non-B40 group, only 3 people or 14.3% were in this category. This shows little difference in uncertainty between the two groups, with the B40 group having a higher uncertainty rate. In the "Dislike" category, the majority of pupils in the B40 group, namely 17 pupils or 58.6%, stated that they do not like vegetables. Meanwhile, in the Non-B40 group, only 2 pupils or 9.5% showed their dislike. This shows that pupils in the B40 group tend to like vegetables less than pupils from the Non-B40 group. Therefore, this analysis shows that socioeconomic status has an influence on the liking of vegetables. Pupils from the Non-B40 group are more likely to like vegetables, while pupils from the B40 group show more dislike.

Table 6. Chi-Square Test Between Vegetable Preference, Gender, and Household Income

Influence	Value	df	p-Value	Result
Gender	0.860	2	0.651	Not significant
Household Income	23.047	2	<.001	Significant

To ensure the reliability of the obtained data, the researcher conducted a chi-square test for independence. In Table 6, the p-value for gender is greater than 0.05, specifically 0.651, indicating that

there is no significant relationship between gender and vegetable preference categories among children. Meanwhile, for household income, the p-value is less than 0.05, specifically <0.001, indicating a significant relationship between household income and vegetable preference categories among children. Therefore, the findings for the second objective conclude that gender does not have a significant impact on vegetable preference categories among children, whereas household income does influence vegetable preference categories among children.

4. DISCUSSION

Findings indicate variations in vegetable preference categories. Broccoli is the most favoured vegetable among first-year pupils. This vegetable may be popular due to its widely accepted taste, high nutritional value, and versatility in cooking (Poelman, A. A. et al., 2017). Previous studies have shown that broccoli, when cooked by boiling or steaming, is well received by children. The inclusion of vegetables in mixed dishes is also preferred. The effect of preparation methods depends on the type of vegetable, as well as the combination of taste and texture, which influences acceptance (Birch, L. L., & Fisher, J. O., 1998). Conversely, eggplant is the least liked vegetable, likely due to its texture or taste, which many find unappealing (Birch, L. L., & Fisher, J. O., 1998). Another factor contributing to vegetable aversion is the widespread availability of snacks and fast food, which children prefer due to their appealing taste and convenience. For the "unsure" category, the percentage is relatively high for vegetables such as cauliflower and sweet potatoes. This suggests that many students may be uncertain about whether they like these vegetables, possibly due to a lack of exposure in their diets. Repeated exposure to vegetables, whether a single type or a variety, can improve children's acceptance (Poelman, A. A. et al., 2017). The study's findings show that more students fall into the "like" category than the "dislike" category, suggesting a positive indicator of early awareness of healthy eating among pupils. However, the number of pupils in the "dislike" category is nearly equal to those who like vegetables, reflecting the challenge of fostering vegetable preference among children. It is recommended to promote the benefits and appealing preparation methods for less favoured vegetables like eggplant and okra. Meanwhile, popular vegetables such as broccoli and carrots should continue to be emphasized. This approach not only enhances vegetable acceptance but also supports balanced nutrition within the community.

Data from Table 4 shows that the difference in vegetable preference between male and female pupils is only 4%. The Chi-square test results in Table 6 also indicate no significant relationship between gender and the level of vegetable preference among children. This suggests that gender does not significantly influence students' vegetable preference. Although the difference is minor, findings still show that female pupils have a slightly higher preference for vegetables than males. This trend is related to children's eating behaviours. Among girls, energy regulation is closely linked to body fat levels; thinner girls tend to regulate their energy intake more accurately than boys, who are more active and expend more energy. Parental control also plays a role in body fat levels, as parents tend to monitor the diets of heavier daughters more closely, encouraging them to eat foods that prevent fat gain, such as vegetables and fruits (Birch, L. L., & Fisher, J. O., 1998). These findings align with studies on the impact of the European School Fruit Scheme in North Rhine-Westphalia, which stated that female pupils consume vegetables more frequently than male pupils due to a stronger preference for vegetables and greater motivation to eat them (Methner, S., Maschkowski, G., & Hartmann, M., 2017).

Children from lower socioeconomic backgrounds who have limited access to vegetables at home tend to have lower vegetable intake rates (Chawner, L. R., et al., 2021). Table 5 shows significant differences in vegetable preference when compared based on socioeconomic status. The Chi-square test results in Table 6 also confirm a significant relationship between socioeconomic status and children's vegetable preference categories. This indicates that socioeconomic factors play a crucial role in shaping children's acceptance of vegetables. A family's socioeconomic status, particularly household income,

influences their children's living conditions. Lower household income is often associated with lower diet quality and food insecurity due to limited access to affordable, nutritious food (French et al., 2019). Communities with lower socioeconomic status tend to consume less nutritious food than higher-status families due to barriers such as the high cost of food, including vegetables (Pechey & Monsivais, 2016).

Additionally, the continuous rise in food prices has significantly increased the Consumer Price Index and inflation rates, which greatly affect people's lives, especially the B40 group, by raising living costs, increasing household expenses, and reducing savings (Eng et al., 2022). Financial constraints and economic pressures make it harder for lower-income families to afford fresh, nutritious food for daily consumption. Conversely, higher income is often linked to better education, which allows parents to have more knowledge about beneficial health practices. Higher income enables parents to provide more nutritious foods, such as fruits and vegetables, supporting their children's growth and health (Rodenburg et al., 2012). Thus, it is hypothesized that parental income and education levels are associated with parenting practices and knowledge about the health benefits of vegetable consumption.

5. CONCLUSION

This study indicates that awareness of the importance of vegetable consumption among children is increasing. However, the main challenge remains their acceptance of various types of vegetables. Factors such as bitterness, unique texture, and preparation methods may be the primary reasons children tend to reject certain vegetables, such as eggplant and okra, while others like broccoli and carrots are more widely accepted. Additionally, gender does not appear to have a significant impact at the early age of seven. In contrast, a family's socioeconomic status plays a crucial role, as children from lower-income households often face barriers in obtaining nutritious food due to high costs and limited access.

The implications of this study emphasize that the data collected serves as a foundation for developing a module to be used in the second phase of the study, aimed at increasing vegetable intake among children. Furthermore, the study provides early insights for teachers regarding vegetable consumption among first-year students. This allows teachers to focus on healthy nutrition education and plan suitable activities for students in school. First-year pupils, in particular, can receive special attention regarding their health and nutrition, enabling schools to collaborate with parents in monitoring and ensuring children's diets are at an optimal level.

A follow-up study will be conducted in the second phase, where researchers will develop a module based on the types of vegetables that are less favoured by first-year pupils. A storytelling approach will be used in the module to shape children's behaviour toward vegetable consumption. Future studies can also explore various vegetable preparation methods that are more appealing to children, such as integrating vegetables into their favourite meals. Additionally, research can examine ways to improve access to quality vegetables for low-income families, including through food subsidy programs or community gardens.

Acknowledgments: I would like to express my deepest gratitude to Fakulti Pendidikan, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, for providing me with the necessary support and resources throughout this journey. Their commitment to academic excellence has been instrumental in shaping my research. My sincere appreciation also goes to Dr. Muhammad Syawal Amran for his invaluable guidance, encouragement, and insightful feedback. His expertise and unwavering support have played a crucial role in refining my work and broadening my perspectives. I am also immensely grateful to my family members for their unconditional love, patience, and motivation. Their continuous support, both emotionally and mentally, has been a driving force in overcoming challenges and completing this endeavor. This achievement would not have been possible without the collective efforts of these individuals, and I am truly thankful for their presence in my academic journey.

References

- Aguiar, I. W. O., Carioca, A. A. F., Barbosa, B. B., Adriano, L. S., Barros, A. Q. S., Kendall, C., & Kerr, L. R. F. S. (2023). Indicadores antropométricos em povos e comunidades tradicionais do Brasil: Análise de registros individuais do Sistema de Vigilância Alimentar e Nutricional, 2019. *Epidemiologia e Serviços de Saúde*, 32, e2023543.
- Allen, I. E., & Seaman, C. A. (2007). Likert scales and data analyses. *Quality progress*, 40(7), 64-65.
- Alkerwi, A. A., Vernier, C., Sauvageot, N., Crichton, G. E., & Elias, M. F. (2015). Demographic and socioeconomic disparity in nutrition: Application of a novel Correlated Component Regression approach. *BMJ Open*, 5(5), e006814.
- Amoadu, M., Abraham, S. A., Adams, A. K., Akoto-Buabeng, W., Obeng, P., & Hagan Jr, J. E. (2024). Risk factors of malnutrition among in-school children and adolescents in developing countries: A scoping review. *Children*, 11(4), 476.
- Andueza, N., Martin-Calvo, N., Navas-Carretero, S., & Cuervo, M. (2022). An intervention in children between 6 and 12 years-old is effective on improving diet quality. *The Alinfa Study*.
- Azizan, N. A., Thangiah, N., Su, T. T., & Majid, H. A. (2018). Does a low-income urban population practise healthy dietary habits?. *International Health*, 10(2), 108-115.
- Bahagian Pemakanan Kementerian Kesehatan Malaysia (2020). *Piramid Makanan Malaysia 2020: Mendidik rakyat mengambil makanan dengan betul*. Retrieved from: <https://www2.moh.gov.my/index.php/pages/view/2725>
- Batabyal, K., Mandal, B., Sarkar, D., Murmu, S., Tamang, A., Das, I., ... & Chattopadhyay, P. S. (2016). Comprehensive assessment of nutrient management technologies for cauliflower production under subtropical conditions. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 79, 1-13.
- Bhuyan, S., Siddhanta, M., Samarendra, N. M., Sarita, B., & Vijay, B. S. (2022). Sweet potato: Its nutritional factor and health benefits. *Biotica Research Today*, 4(6), 450-452.
- Birch, L. L., & Fisher, J. O. (1998). Development of eating behaviors among children and adolescents. *Pediatrics*, 101(Supplement_2), 539-549.
- Bourke, C. D., Berkley, J. A., & Prendergast, A. J. (2016). Immune dysfunction as a cause and consequence of malnutrition. *Trends in Immunology*, 37(6), 386-398.
- Chawner, L. R., Blundell-Birtill, P., & Hetherington, M. M. (2021). Predictors of vegetable consumption in children and adolescents: Analyses of the UK National Diet and Nutrition Survey (2008–2017). *British Journal of Nutrition*, 126(2), 295-306.
- Chong, K. H., Lee, S. T., Ng, S. A., Khouw, I., & Poh, B. K. (2017). Fruit and vegetable intake patterns and their associations with sociodemographic characteristics, anthropometric status and nutrient intake profiles among Malaysian children aged 1–6 years. *Nutrients*, 9(8), 723.
- Cieza, A., Causey, K., Kamenov, K., Hanson, S. W., Chatterji, S., & Vos, T. (2020). Global estimates of the need for rehabilitation based on the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019: A systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *The Lancet*, 396(10267), 2006-2017.
- De, P., & Chattopadhyay, N. (2019). Effects of malnutrition on child development: Evidence from a backward district of India. *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*, 7(3), 439-445.
- Eng, C. W., Lim, S. C., Ngongo, C., Sham, Z. H., Kataria, I., Chandran, A., & Mustapha, F. I. (2022). Dietary practices, food purchasing, and perceptions about healthy food availability and affordability: a cross-sectional study of low-income Malaysian adults. *BMC Public Health*, 22(1), 192.

- Folkvord, F., Naderer, B., Coates, A., & Boyland, E. (2021). Promoting fruit and vegetable consumption for childhood obesity prevention. *Nutrients*, 14(1), 157.
- French, S. A., Tangney, C. C., Crane, M. M., Wang, Y., & Appelhans, B. M. (2019). Nutrition quality of food purchases varies by household income: the SHoPPER study. *BMC Public Health*, 19, 1-7.
- Fynn-Sackey, U. A., & Abdul Salam, M. (2015). Effects of malnutrition among children in SubSaharan Africa and Southern Asia.
- Haines, J., Haycraft, E., Lytle, L., Nicklaus, S., Kok, F. J., Merdji, M., ... & Hughes, S. O. (2019). Nurturing children's healthy eating: Position statement. *Appetite*, 137, 124-133.
- Hendrie, G. A., Anastasiou, K., Brindal, E., Wiggins, B., Baird, D. L., Johnson, B. J., ... & Golley, R. K. (2024). Increasing children's vegetable consumption: translating a review of the evidence base to develop best practice guidelines. *AJPM Focus*, 3(4), 100229.
- Huang, Y., Edirisinghe, I., & Burton-Freeman, B. M. (2016). Low-income shoppers and fruit and vegetables: what do they think? *Nutrition Today*, 51(5), 242-250.
- Jabatan Perangkaan Malaysia (2023a): *Pendapatan Perbelanjaan Kemiskinan Ketidaksamarataan 2022*. Putrajaya: Jabatan Perangkaan Malaysia 334p.
- Katembu, S., Zahedi, A., Sind, S. M., Sommer, U., Kimamo, C., & Sommer, W. (2024). The impact of fairytale stories on the food choices of preschool children. medRxiv, 2024-10.
- Kirolos, A., Goyheneix, M., Elias, M. K., Chisala, M., Lissauer, S., Gladstone, M., & Kerac, M. (2022). Neurodevelopmental, cognitive, behavioural and mental health impairments following childhood malnutrition: a systematic review. *BMJ Global Health*, 7(7), e009330.
- Koo, H. C., Poh, B. K., Lee, S. T., Chong, K. H., Bragt, M. C., & Abd, T. R. (2016). Are Malaysian children achieving dietary guideline recommendations? *Asia Pacific Journal of Public Health*, 28(5_suppl), 8S-20S.
- Mallick, P. K. (2022). Evaluating potential importance of cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.-Cucurbitaceae): A brief review.
- Methner, S., Maschkowski, G., & Hartmann, M. (2017). The European School Fruit Scheme: Impact on children's fruit and vegetable consumption in North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany. *Public Health Nutrition*, 20(3), 542-548.
- Mihrshahi, S., Myton, R., Partridge, S. R., Esdaile, E., Hardy, L. L., & Gale, J. (2019). Sustained low consumption of fruit and vegetables in Australian children: Findings from the Australian National Health Surveys. *Health Promotion Journal of Australia*, 30(1), 83-87.
- Naeem, M. Y., & Ugur, S. (2019). Nutritional content and health benefits of eggplant. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture-Food Science and Technology*, 7, 31-36.
- Nekitsing, C., Hetherington, M. M., & Blundell-Birtill, P. (2018). Developing healthy food preferences in preschool children through taste exposure, sensory learning, and nutrition education. *Current Obesity Reports*, 7, 60-67.
- Owushi, J. N., & Asanga, D. E. (2024). Assessment of human health improved fruits and vegetables: The benefits for growing children. *The Peerian Journal*, 27, 117-129.
- Pechey, R., & Monsivais, P. (2016). Socioeconomic inequalities in the healthiness of food choices: Exploring the contributions of food expenditures. *Preventive Medicine*, 88, 203-209.
- Poelman, A. A., Delahunty, C. M., & de Graaf, C. (2017). Vegetables and other core food groups: A comparison of key flavour and texture properties. *Food Quality and Preference*, 56, 1-7.

- Razak, N. A. (2021). *Food and Nutrition in Malaysian Children*. Retrieved from: <https://www.nestlenutrition-institute.org/publication-series/food-and-nutrition-malaysian-children>
- Rodenburg, G., Oenema, A., Kremers, S. P., & van de Mheen, D. (2012). Parental and child fruit consumption in the context of general parenting, parental education and ethnic background. *Appetite*, 58(1), 364-372.
- Shinwell, J., & Defeyter, M. A. (2021). Food insecurity: A constant factor in the lives of low-income families in Scotland and England. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9, 588254.
- Singh, D. N., Bohra, J. S., Dubey, T. P., Shivahre, P. R., Singh, R. K., Singh, T., & Jaiswal, D. K. (2023). Common foods for boosting human immunity: A review. *Food Science & Nutrition*, 11(11), 6761-6774.
- Song, S., Ishdorj, A., & Dave, J. M. (2021). Gender differences in nutritional quality and consumption of lunches brought from home to school. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(24), 13168.
- Ştefan, I. M. A., & Ona, A. D. (2020). Cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* L.). overview of the health benefits and therapeutical uses.
- Takona, J. P. (2024). Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches. *Quality & Quantity*, 58(1), 1011-1013.
- Tan, A. K., Yen, S. T., Hasan, A. R., & Muhamed, K. (2014). Household expenditures on vegetables in Malaysia. *Journal of Agricultural and Applied Economics*, 46(4), 615-634.
- Wertheim-Heck, S., Raneri, J. E., & Oosterveer, P. (2019). Food safety and nutrition for low-income urbanites: exploring a social justice dilemma in consumption policy. *Environment and Urbanization*, 31(2), 397-420.
- World Health Organization. (2022a). *Report on the fifth round of data collection, 2018–2020: WHO European childhood obesity Surveillance Initiative (COSI)*.
- Zubiaga, M. R. O. (2024). *Nutrition and Academic Achievement of Filipino Learners in Balutakay Elementary School, East District Of Bansalan*.